

ULTRAVIOLET TO NEAR-INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY OF REE-BEARING MATERIALS

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1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing worldwide demand for many of our natural resources requires that we reassess our geologic models and expand our search for rare earth element (REE) resources in the United States. Currently, there is a lack of sufficient spectroscopic investigations characterizing surface materials associated with many of the potential REE-bearing deposit types. Understanding the spectral properties of these deposits using ultraviolet (UV) to near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopic methods will add significant information about how we assess such deposits in the future using laboratory spectrometers, core scanning systems, and imaging spectrometers. Spectra of lanthanide-bearing materials show fine structure in the UV to NIR wavelengths of the electromagnetic spectrum that are caused by $4f-4f$ intraconfigurational electron transitions of lanthanide ions present in the material [1]. Lanthanide-bearing minerals produce sharp spectral absorptions that allow for accurate identification of these minerals when found in significant concentrations and can also be used to identify the type of lanthanides based on the position of their absorptions.

2. BACKGROUND

The term lanthanides refers to the fifteen elements with atomic numbers between 57 (La) and 71 (Lu) while the term rare earths is used in reference to Yttrium (39) and Scandium (21) in addition to the lanthanide series elements. Of the trivalent REE ions, La^{3+} , Lu^{3+} , Y^{3+} and Sc^{3+} are not spectroscopically active in the UV to NIR wavelengths due to an empty or filled $4f$ orbital [2]. Diagnostic $4f^n - 4f^n$ transition absorptions,

caused by crystal field interactions, have been observed in the UV to NIR region of the electromagnetic spectrum in many common lanthanide-bearing materials [1],[3],[4],[5]. The partial filling of the $4f$ electron shell combined with a shielding effect caused by the fully filled $5s^25p^6$ -electron shells makes lanthanide ions and their absorptions unique.

3. METHODS

Synthetic single REE phosphates, carbonates, oxides, hydroxides, chlorides and glasses have been measured in the laboratory to identify absorption positions that are characteristic of each REE as they occur in different materials (Fig. 1). While these analyses help determine the band positions of individual ions, naturally occurring REE minerals (i.e., monazite, xenotime, apatite, eudialyte, etc.) are spectrally complex because they usually contain multiple lanthanide ions in variable proportions. Therefore, a large suite of REE-bearing minerals has been measured from various USGS collections. Because spectral resolution is critical to identifying narrow absorption features and any shifts in band positions, these materials have been measured on several different high resolution spectrometers. Using a combination of Ocean Optics USB 2000+ UV-VIS*, USB2000+ VIS-NIR and ASD FieldSpec 4 spectrometers, REE-bearing materials have been characterized from 0.2 to 2.5 microns with a spectral resolution of ~ 1.5 nm between 0.2 and 1.0 microns and 11 to 12 nm between 1.0 and 2.5 microns. Core, rock chips, billets, sediment samples and grab samples

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were manually scanned with a laboratory spectrometer to identify the most intense or spectrally different lanthanide features within the samples. Mineral specimens were subsampled for X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis to determine their mineralogical composition and analyzed with LA ICP-MS, electron microprobe, and ICP-MS to determine their REE chemistry.

4. DATA SUMMARY

To date, approximately 80 single element REE standards and over 40 REE-bearing mineral samples have been analyzed (Fig. 2). Results suggest that variations in the degree of crystal field splitting, which influences the number of bands and thus the spectral shape of their overlapping absorptions, allows for the spectral differentiation between REE-bearing minerals. In addition to the synthetic compounds and mineral samples, a suite of apatite samples were analyzed to observe the changes in band intensities as a function of lanthanide concentration within the samples. The spectra have been combined into a database that is now being used for spectral comparisons to laboratory, core scanning, and imaging spectrometer data. To support these results, a comprehensive suite of rocks and minerals from marine phosphates, paleo-beach placers, Iron Oxide Copper-Gold (IOCG) deposits, alkaline to peralkaline igneous complexes, pegmatites (associated with alkaline magmas and carbonatite intrusives), have been measured and compared to the spectral database. While REE-bearing minerals from around the world have been measured, we focused our efforts on characterizing samples from deposits associated with ongoing USGS projects related to phosphates from the southeast region of the United States, beach placers from the east coast of the United States, Bokan

Mountain in Alaska, the Pea Ridge area of Missouri, Mountain Pass in California, and Elk Creek in Nebraska. Results from the spectroscopic investigation of lanthanide-bearing materials and the comparisons of those materials to REE deposits of the U.S. will be presented.

5. REFERENCES

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Figure 1.) Spectra of selected single element lanthanide oxides.

Figure 2.) Seven REE-bearing mineral spectra showing the variability of diagnostic lanthanide $4f$ - $4f$ absorption features over the visible to near-infrared portions of the electromagnetic spectrum.